

DMP for Use case 2 - Forest monitoring (Bosmonitoring)

Version : v3 - 13 September 2024

This Data Management Plan aims to provide a brief description of the model and datasets associated with use case 2 - Forest monitoring.

DMP Authors/Contacts

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Main stakeholder: INBO (Kris Vandekerkhove) & ANB (Leen Govaere)

DMP Language

English

1 Brief description of the use case

Information on tree species is important to support policy, management, and research. The Regional Forest Inventory of Flanders delivers crucial ground-based measurements on the status and long-term evolution of forests in Flanders. However, such measurements only allow for statistical evaluation over longer time periods on the regional scale of Flanders. In this context, satellite-based approaches offer the opportunity to generate maps containing up-to-date and spatially-explicit information on forests. In this use case, the core objective is to generate maps of frequently-occurring tree species in Flanders with Sentinel-2 time series.

1.1 What needs to be monitored?

The stakeholders are interested in the state and evolutions of forests in Flanders, specifically performing **dominant tree species classification**. This monitoring focuses on eight dominant species:

- Scots pine
- Black pine,
- Common and sessile oak
- Poplar
- Beech
- Common alder
- Birch
- Northern red oak.

These classes reflect the most frequently occurring species in the region. A tree species is considered dominant when it occupies 80% or more of the basal area within a plot. The stakeholder is particularly interested in the conversion from conifer to broadleaved stands.. Finally, the stakeholder is interested in updating the 1990/2000 forest stand map (Bosreferentielaag), which has not been updated since.

1.2 Where should it be monitored?

Forest cover in Flanders, according to the *Digitale Boswijzer Vlaanderen 2021*¹

1.3 How often should it be monitored?

Yearly.

2 Modeling approach

2.1 What type of deep learning problem?

Time series classification: Outputs one label for one time series

2.2 Which model type(s) were used?

- **Random Forest (RF):** This algorithm utilizes an ensemble of numerous decision trees to reach a single classification result. It is particularly robust for remote sensing because it handles imbalanced data and high-dimensional spectral inputs effectively
- **Support Vector Machine (SVM):** This model identifies an optimal hyperplane or decision boundary that maximizes the separation between different tree species classes based on the training data. It was found to be highly accurate for specific baseline years like 2018.
- **Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP):** A type of feedforward artificial neural network consisting of multiple layers of fully connected neurons with nonlinear activation functions. In this project, it benefited the most from multi-year training data to capture interannual spectral variations.

The output data described in section 3.2 were obtained with a year-specific random forest model.

3 Data

3.1 Description of the input data

The primary satellite source is the TERRASCOPE_S2_TOC_V2 collection, providing Sentinel-2 Level-2A imagery processed with the Sen2Cor processor. From this, ten spectral bands were selected for their relevance to tree species identification (B02, B03, B04, B05, B06, B07, B08, B8A, B11, and B12), along with the calculated NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index). These satellite observations were aggregated into regularly spaced monthly or dekadal intervals, linearly interpolated and smoothed using a Savitzky-Golay filter to create a clean, comparable time series.

3.2 Description of the output data

3.2.1 Dataset 1

Dataset name or title: Bosmonitoring-boomsoort_Sxxx_Syyy_YYYY-MM-DD.tif

xxx and yyy refer to the geographical subdivision into three subsections: S001-S054, S055-S117 and S118-S172.

YYYY-MM-DD is the date of the predictions, it is always set to MM-DD = 01-01, for each year from 2018 to 2022

¹ <https://www.vlaanderen.be/datavindplaats/catalogus/digitale-boswijzer-vlaanderen-2021>

Dataset abstract:

This dataset provides high-resolution (20m) raster layers characterizing the main tree type for each year (2018-2022) across forest pixels in Flanders, Belgium. Developed within the framework of the GEO.INFORMED project, the data supports the monitoring of European Forests.

Dataset locator: on INBO Google Drive under PRJ_GEO.INFORMED > Research & collaboration > Outputs > Processed outputs > Bossamenstelling > YEAR >

Resource language: Dutch

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

ben.somers@kuleuven.be

<https://geo-informed.be/>

Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

margot.vanpoucke@kuleuven.be

Data format: .tif (geotiff)

Geometry: Raster

Coordinate reference system (CRS): EPSG:3857 - WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator

Geographic bounding box (WGS84): outline of Flanders

Temporal extent: 2018-2022

Date of last revision: 30/09/2024

Lineage: Derived from Sentinel-2 monthly time series with a UDF described in the associated workflow documentation.

Bands: 8 bands with prediction probability, one for each main tree type: Grove den (band1), Corsicaanse den (band2), Inlandse eik (band3), Populier (band4), Beuk (band5), Zwarte els (band6), Berk (band7), Amerikaanse eik (band8)

Quality flags: none

Size of the dataset: 880 MB (per yearly output)

Accessibility: Available on request from Margot Verhulst or Ben Somers

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any): Cannot be made publicly available due to privacy regulations

How will the data be stored and backed up?

Output rasters are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) 'PRJ_GEO.INFORMED' and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files? No

3.3 Description of the reference data

The main source of reference data for this use case is the **Regional Forest Inventory of Flanders**, collected by ANB (NL: Agentschap voor Natuur en Bos, EN: Agency for Nature and Forests) of the Flemish Government. For this study, data from the second (2009-2019) and the third (2019-present) were used. This dataset provided plot-level variables such as species-specific basal area to identify the eight dominant target classes. To ensure data quality, these plots were filtered using the Digitale Boswijzer Vlaanderen 2021 to verify forest cover and an auxiliary INBO change map to exclude areas that had recently undergone deforestation.

3.3.1 Dataset 1

Dataset name or title: (Short) name or title of the dataset

EN: Regional Forest Inventory of Flanders (RFI)

NL: Vlaamse Bosinventaris (VBI)

Dataset abstract:

The main source of reference data for this use case is the Regional Forest Inventory of Flanders, a measurement network coordinated by ANB (NL: Agentschap voor Natuur en Bos, EN: Agency for Nature and Forests) of the Flemish Government. This is a policy-supporting network for all forests in Flanders and is legally supported in the Forest Decree (Art. 41 quarter). The first measurements were carried out in 1997. Spatially, the sampling design is based on a fixed grid of 0.5 by 1 km over Flanders. This yields 27,163 points of which roughly one tenth are located within forests. In time, one measurement cycle takes 10 years, meaning that each plot is visited every 10 years. Each year, roughly one tenth of the plots are visited. Each plot is visited at least twice per year, once in summer for vegetation measurements and one in winter for dendrological measurements. Some plots are visited a third time for additional vegetation measurements, depending on specific conditions.

Dataset locator:

This dataset is not publicly available. On [this page](#), a template for a data agreement can be found. The people to contact are: leen.govaere@vlaanderen.be and/or anja.leyman@vlaanderen.be

Resource language: Dutch/English (sometimes mixed)

Research team contact for the dataset (business owner/contact/PI):

Data owner: ANB (NL: Agentschap voor Natuur en Bos, EN: Agency for Nature and Forests)

leen.govaere@vlaanderen.be

<https://www.natuurenbos.be/dossiers/bosinventaris#toc-contact>

Support team contact for the dataset (database manager/contact):

<https://www.natuurenbos.be/dossiers/bosinventaris#toc-contact>

Data format: .csv and .xlsx

Data was provided on three occasions (22/12/2020, 07/02/2023, 14/10/2024)

The names of the files delivered on 22/12/2020:

- tbl0Boom.csv
- tbl10bisBoomsoortenPlot_KUL.csv
- tbl10Boomsoorten_KUL.csv
- tbl11VegetatieSamenstelling_KUL.csv
- tbl12BmsDiamKlasse.csv
- tbl2BestandskaraktKwal_KUL.csv
- tbl3BestandskaraktKwant_KUL.csv
- tbl3bisBestandskaraktKwantPlot_KUL.csv
- tbl4Vegetatie.csv
- tbl5RuimtelijkeIndices_KUL.csv
- tbl6DoodHout_KUL.csv
- tbl7a_AI_Bosstructuur_VBI1.csv
- tbl7b_AI_Bosstructuur_VBI2.csv
- tbl7c_AI_Woodlayer_VBI1.csv
- tbl7d_AI_WoodLayer_VBI2.csv
- tbl7g_AI_DeadWood_VBI1.csv
- tbl7h_AI_DeadWood_VBI2.csv
- tblCoordinaten_KUL.csv
- tblPlotDetails_KUL.csv
- tblPlotWeights_KUL.csv
- tblStrataDynamic_KUL.csv
- tblTreeSpeciesCharacteristics.xlsx

The names of the files delivered on 07/02/2023 (these files encompass the measurements that were already provided on 22/12/2020):

- tblCoordinaten_KUL_20230206.csv
- tblPlotDetails_KUL_20230206.csv
- tblPlotWeights_KUL_20230206.csv
- tblStrataDynamic_KUL_20230206.csv
- tbl0Boom_KUL_20230206.csv
- tbl2BestandskaraktKwal_KUL_20230206.csv
- tbl3BestandskaraktKwant_KUL_20230206.csv
- tbl3bisBestandskaraktKwantPlot_KUL_20230206.csv
- tbl6Doodhout_KUL_20230206.csv
- tbl10Boomsoorten_KUL_20230206.csv
- tbl10bisBoomsoorten_KUL_20230206.csv

The names of the files delivered on 14/10/2024 (again these files encompass the measurement that were already provided):

- tblCoordinaten_KUL_20241014.csv
- tblPlotDetails_KUL_20241014.csv
- tblPlotWeights_KUL_20241014.csv
- tblStrataDynamic_KUL_20241014.csv
- tbl0Boom_KUL_20241014.csv
- tbl2BestandskaraktKwal_KUL_20241014.csv

- tbl3BestandkaraktKwant_KUL_20241014.csv
- tbl3bisBestandkaraktKwantPlot_KUL_20241014.csv
- tbl6Doodhout_KUL_20241014.csv
- tbl10Boomsoorten_KUL_20241014.csv
- tbl10bisBoomsoorten_KUL_20241014.csv

Geometry: Not applicable (.csv or .xlsx files)

However, X and Y point coordinates indicating the middle of the plot are provided in the file “tblCoordinaten_KUL_20230206.csv”, which can be used to generate point geometries. Polygon geometries may be generated by applying a circular buffer to those points. **These coordinates should not be made public under any circumstance.**

Coordinate reference system (CRS): Lambert72

Geographic bounding box (WGS84): bounding box Flanders

- *westBoundLongitude:* 2.56035
- *eastBoundLongitude:* 5.92000
- *southBoundLatitude:* 50.67480
- *northBoundLatitude:* 51.49590

Temporal extent:

- First measurement period: 1997-1999
- Second measurement period: 2009-2019
- Third measurement period: 2019-present
 - Data obtained: 2019-2022 (last date: 31/03/2022)

Date of last revision: 2022

Lineage: for more information, see here:

https://natuurenbos.be/sites/default/files/2023-06/handleiding_bosinventarisatie_2.pdf

Attributes: for more information, see here:

https://natuurenbos.be/sites/default/files/2023-06/handleiding_bosinventarisatie_2.pdf

Quality flags (if available): Not available

Number of samples in the dataset:

- Second measurement period:
 - Total number of plots: 2746 plots
 - Plots visited: 2699 (however NAs present for some attributes)
- Third measurement period:
 - Total number of plots: 969 plots
 - Plots visited: 810 (however NAs present for some attributes)

Size of the dataset (MB): 50 MB

Screenshot of attribute table: Example from tbl2BestandkaraktKwal_KUL_20230206.csv

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V
1	IDPlots	Periode	IDSegments	v2_StandType	v3_HarvestType	v4_MixType	v5_StandAge	v6_WindThrow	v7_ForestEdge	v8_ForestOvergang	PlotWeight	SegmentWeight	StartPeriode	IDGroup	DateDendro							
2	105108;1;1	naaldhout	hooghout	stamsgewijs	ongelijkjarig	NA	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	105108_1	1999											
3	105108;2;1	gemengd loofhout	hooghout	stamsgewijs	61 - 80 jaar	2	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	105108_1	2014											
4	105115;2;169;1;2	105115_2	2014																			
5	105122;1;1	naaldhout	hooghout	homogeen	41 - 60 jaar	NA	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	105122_1	1999											
6	105122;2;1	naaldhout	hooghout	homogeen	41 - 60 jaar	2	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	105122_1	2014											
7	105123;1;1	naaldhout	hooghout	stamsgewijs	21 - 40 jaar	NA	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	105123_1	1999											
8	105123;2;1	naaldhout	hooghout	stamsgewijs	61 - 80 jaar	2	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	105123_1	2014											
9	105124;1;1	naaldhout	hooghout	stamsgewijs	1 - 20 jaar	NA	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	105124_1	1999											
10	105124;2;1	naaldhout	hooghout	stamsgewijs	21 - 40 jaar	2	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	105124_1	2014											
11	105130;1;1	naaldhout	hooghout	homogeen	1 - 20 jaar	NA	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	105130_1	1999											
12	105130;2;1	naaldhout	hooghout	stamsgewijs	21 - 40 jaar	2	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	105130_1	2014											
13	105131;1;1	naaldhout	hooghout	homogeen	41 - 60 jaar	NA	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	105131_1	1999											
14	105131;2;1	naaldhout	hooghout	homogeen	41 - 60 jaar	2	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	105131_1	2014											
15	105132;2;19;1;2	105132_2	2014																			
16	105138;2;1	loofhout	hooghout	stamsgewijs	21 - 40 jaar	2	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;2	105138_2	2014											
17	105148;1;1	naaldhout	hooghout	stamsgewijs	1 - 20 jaar	NA	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	105148_1	1999											
18	105148;2;1	naaldhout	hooghout	homogeen	21 - 40 jaar	1	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	105148_1	2014											
19	105156;2;1	naaldhout	hooghout	stamsgewijs	61 - 80 jaar	2	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;2	105156_2	2014											
20	117136;2;156;1;2	117136_2	2016																			
21	117149;2;1	loofhout	middelhout	stamsgewijs	31 - 100 jaar	NA	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;2	117149_2	2016											
22	117144;1;1	loofhout	hooghout	stamsgewijs	ongelijkjarig	NA	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	117144_1	1998											
23	117144;2;1	loofhout	hooghout	stamsgewijs	61 - 80 jaar	2	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	117144_1	2016											
24	117149;2;1	gemengd loofhout	NA	NA	1 - 20 jaar	2	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;2	117149_2	2016											
25	117151;2;1	loofhout	NA	stamsgewijs	21 - 40 jaar	2	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;2	117151_2	2015											
26	117157;2;1	loofhout	hooghout	stamsgewijs	41 - 60 jaar	NA	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;2	117157_2	2015											
27	118084;2;178;1;2	118084_2	2015																			
28	118093;2;179;1;2	118093_2	2014																			
29	118121;2;156;1;2	118121_2	2015																			
30	124141;1;1	gemengd naaldhout	hooghout	groepsgewijs	ongelijkjarig	NA	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	124141_1	1999											
31	124141;2;1	loofhout	hooghout	stamsgewijs	61 - 100 jaar	2	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	124141_1	2017											
32	124149;1;1	gemengd loofhout	hooghout	stamsgewijs	ongelijkjarig	NA	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	124149_1	1999											
33	124149;2;1	loofhout	hooghout	stamsgewijs	61 - 80 jaar	1	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	124149_1	2018											
34	124152;1;1	loofhout	middelhout	Niet bepaald	ongelijkjarig	NA	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	124152_1	1999											
35	124152;2;1	loofhout	hooghout	stamsgewijs	101 - 120 jaar	NA	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	124152_1	2017											
36	128008;1;1	naaldhout	hooghout	homogeen	31 - 40 jaar	NA	FALSE	FALSE	1;1;1	128008_1	1999											

Accessibility: Available on request from ANB:

<https://www.natuurenbos.be/beleid-wetgeving/natuurbeheer/bosinventaris/contact>

License (if applicable): User agreement between KUL-FNL and ANB

Restrictions on making the data publicly available (if any): Yes, restrictions apply. We cannot make this data publicly available.

How and when will the data be made publicly available? (If this is not yet the case): Not applicable

How will the data be stored and backed up? Reference data are stored in the Shared Drive (Google Drive) PRJ_GEO.INFORMED and automatically backed-up.

Are there any accompanying files?